

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER CHARACTERISTICS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION: A SEM APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to empirically investigate the influence of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention by employing a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) framework. By analyzing the multifaceted relationships between specific influencer traits and consumer intentions, this research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how influencer attributes shape consumers' decisions to purchase products or services.

Design/methodology/approach: This study will adopt a quantitative research design. Data will be collected through surveys distributed to a diverse sample of social media users. The survey instrument will be designed to measure various social media influencer characteristics, including authenticity, expertise, reliability, and trustworthiness. Participants will also be queried about their recent purchase intentions influenced by social media content. The collected data will be subjected to Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), a statistical technique that allows for the assessment of complex relationships between latent variables. SEM will help identify the direct and indirect effects of influencer characteristics on purchase intention.

Findings: The results revealed that social media Characteristics have a significant Impact on the Purchase Intention of users. Additionally, the sub-constructs have also shown a significant impact on the Purchase Intention of the users like attractiveness, Expertise, Trustworthiness.

Practical implications: This study has two applications in real life. First, it will provide businesses and marketers with useful information that will enable them to determine which influencer traits are most effective at influencing consumer purchase intention. Utilizing this information, businesses can create influencer marketing programs that are more successful and generate a higher return on investment. Second, since consumers would have a greater knowledge of the persuasive strategies used by social media influencers, they will be better equipped to make purchases in a market where influencer content is abundant.

Originality/value: This study contributes to the field by offering a novel approach to understanding the influence of social media influencers on consumer behavior. The utilization of SEM to analyze the relationship between influencer characteristics and purchase intention is a unique aspect of this research. The insights generated from this study

will advance the understanding of influencer marketing dynamics, providing a valuable resource for academia, businesses, and consumers seeking to navigate the complex landscape of digital marketing.

Keywords: *Social Media Influencers, Influencer Characteristics, Consumer Purchase Intention, Social Media Marketing, Authenticity & SEM*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving digital era, social media platforms have transformed the way individuals interact, communicate, and engage with content. What began as a means of connecting with friends and sharing personal updates has, over time, evolved into a powerful force that significantly influences consumer behavior and purchase decisions (Adam & Dzang Alhassan, 2020). Social media, with its unparalleled reach and ability to foster connections and communities, plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer purchase intention. Social media's widespread influence on today's digital environment has completely changed how individuals communicate, share information, and make purchases (Jaitly & Gautam, 2021). The development of social media influencers, who have transcended conventional advertising channels to become potent moulders of consumer preferences and behaviors, is a crucial aspect of this transition. Social media influencers have quickly emerged as key players in the world of marketing and brand promotion as millions of people all over the world use sites like Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok to find material that speaks to their interests and goals (Zeng et al., 2022a). The ascendancy of social media influencers, whose online personas often revolve around lifestyle, fashion, beauty, travel, and various other niches, has created a unique landscape for businesses and marketers to engage with their target audiences (Zeng et al., 2022b). These individuals, known for their authenticity and reliability, have cultivated dedicated followings that trust their recommendations and opinions, turning them into invaluable intermediaries between brands and consumers. Recognizing the potential influence of these digital trendsetters, companies are increasingly partnering with them to drive consumer purchase intention and, ultimately, sales (Xie et al., 2022). By examining the impact of social media influencer traits on customer purchase intention, this study aims to delve deeply into the complex dynamics of these emerging phenomena.

The goal of the study is to examine how influential people's unique characteristics, behaviors, and communication methods impact the attitudes and actions of their followers (Li et al., 2023). Both organizations' looking to optimize their influencer marketing efforts and consumers hoping to make informed purchasing decisions in an increasingly linked digital environment must understand these linkages (Ganbold & Gantulga, 2023). The most notable aspect of the 21st century is the emergence of social media, which has ushered in a period of unmatched connectedness and information sharing. Social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat have objectives beyond just connecting friends and sharing updates on daily life (Gonçalves et al., 2023). They have developed into comprehensive platforms for the production, curation, and consumption of content, supporting a wide variety of media types like text, photos, videos, and live streaming (Shamsi & Abad, 2023).

Social media has a stunning global adoption rate, with billions of individuals actively using these platforms every day. One of the most profound impacts of social media is its ability to shape consumer attitudes and purchase intentions (Tilahun et al., 2023). Individuals today often turn to social media for a multitude of purposes, including seeking product recommendations, conducting research, and evaluating the opinions of peers and influencers. Social media has become a virtual marketplace where consumers can engage with brands,

products, and services. This interaction, in turn, significantly influences their likelihood to purchase (Kroker-Lobos et al., 2023). The concept of "purchase intention" refers to the predisposition of a consumer to buy a product or service. It encompasses a range of cognitive and emotional factors that guide the decision-making process. In the context of social media, purchase intention is not just a reflection of the product's inherent qualities but is also influenced by the myriad information, endorsements, and opinions that individuals encounter within their social media feeds. Influencers on social media, who have gained notoriety as captivating figures with sizable fan bases, have a significant impact on consumers' purchase intentions (Limbu et al., 2023). Their recommendations, videos, and posts frequently have a personal touch that connects with their audience. Consumer behavior may be significantly affected by this close personal connection and the perceived sincerity of their recommendations. Influencers frequently act as go-betweens, promoting consumer brand engagement and product discovery (dos Santos et al., 2023). A crucial component of this dynamic interaction is comprehending how these influencers affect consumers' intentions to make purchases.

The complex relationships between social media and purchasing intention are the focus of this study. With a focus on the function of social media influencers, it will examine the many methods by which social media platforms affect the choices and actions of consumers. Understanding the fundamental mechanisms will help businesses better customize their marketing campaigns, and consumers will be better equipped to make decisions in a world overflowing with persuasive information (Stranieri et al., 2023). We will go into the many dimensions of this complicated connection in the parts that follow, looking at the influence of various social media platforms, the psychology of buy intention, and the tactics used by influencers to sway consumer decisions (Dinh et al., 2023). Through this investigation, we hope to shed light on how consumer behavior is changing in the digital era and provide useful information for companies, marketers, and customers navigating this dynamic and constantly changing environment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social media platforms have evolved into powerful communication channels. Users can share text, images, videos, and more, facilitating interactions with individuals, communities, and organizations (Jamil et al., 2023). The inherent interconnectedness and immediacy of social media enable information dissemination in real time. According to research, social media affects interpersonal interactions. Social media platforms, according to Ellison, (Al-Gasawneh, Hasan, et al., 2023) research, support and strengthen relationships between people who are geographically separated. They simultaneously introduce challenges, such as problems managing boundaries in romantic relationships and privacy-related issues (Al-Gasawneh, AlZubi, et al., 2023).

In today's digital age, social media platforms have emerged as influential arenas where consumers seek information, share experiences, and make purchasing decisions. Within this context, social media influencers have become instrumental in guiding consumer purchase intention (Bushara et al., 2023). This section delves into existing literature to explore the intricate relationships between social media influencer characteristics and consumer behavior. Social media influencers are a new breed of digital opinion leaders that have emerged as a result of the growth of social media. These people have sizable fan bases on websites like Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok, which they use to promote goods, services, and lifestyles. Their perceived honesty and the close relationships they build with their viewers are the main reasons for their appeal (Tan et al., 2023). Because of this, social media influencers are now crucial elements of modern marketing plans. Authenticity is a critical factor that strongly

affects consumers' intentions to make purchases.

Influencers are frequently praised for their openness, sincerity, and capacity to establish a personal connection with their fans (Anas et al., 2023). According to research, customers are more likely to believe influencers who come across as sincere and real, which in turn affects their decision to buy the goods or services they suggest (Armawan et al., 2023). Another crucial influencer characteristic is expertise in a specific domain. Influencers often establish credibility by demonstrating deep knowledge and competence within a particular niche (Al-Mu'ani et al., 2023). Consumers tend to trust influencers who are perceived as experts in their fields, leading to increased purchase intention for products or services endorsed within that niche. The reliability of influencers, in addition to honesty and knowledge, is crucial in determining how consumers' intentions are shaped. According to (Alsoud et al., 2023) reliability is the capacity of an influencer to establish a connection with their audience through like interests, values, or lifestyles. As followers identify with their influencers, making buy recommendations more persuasive, relatable influencers tend to have a greater impact on consumer behavior (Yanuar et al., 2022). Trustworthiness is a fundamental influencer characteristic that directly affects consumer purchase intention (Salhab et al., 2023). When influencers maintain a consistent and reliable persona, it bolsters trust among their followers. The trustworthiness of an influencer extends to their endorsements, which can sway consumer decisions and increase their propensity to purchase recommended products (Cayaban et al., 2023).

Social media is integral to contemporary business operations. It serves as a dynamic marketing tool, allowing businesses to connect with audiences, build brand identity, and engage in customer relationship management (Rivera-Eraso et al., 2023). Social media analytics enable companies to gain insights into consumer behavior and preferences. The rapid spread of information, both accurate and false, is a hallmark of social media. False information, often referred to as "fake news," can proliferate quickly and influence public opinion (Ginting & Yusriadi, 2023). The ability to disseminate information on a global scale is a double-edged sword with profound societal implications (Municipality, 2023). The existing literature underscores the pivotal role of social media influencer characteristics in shaping consumer purchase intention. Attributes such as authenticity, expertise, reliability, and trustworthiness wield significant influence over consumers' decisions (Chen & Chang, 2023). Acknowledging the multifaceted interplay between these characteristics is essential for businesses and marketers seeking to harness the potential of influencer marketing in the digital age (Tilahun et al., 2023). This review provides a solid foundation for our study, which will employ Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to explore these relationships further, contributing to a deeper understanding of the intricate dynamics that drive consumer behavior in the era of social media influence.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Objective

The purpose of this study is to empirically investigate the influence of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention by employing a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) framework. By analyzing the multifaceted relationships between specific influencer traits and consumer intentions, this research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how influencer attributes shape consumers' decisions to purchase products or services.

Hypothesis Developed

H1: Social Media Characteristics have a significant impact on Purchase Intentions.

H2: Trustworthiness has a significant impact on Purchase Intentions.

H3: Attractiveness has a significant impact on Purchase Intention.

H4: Product Match-Up has a significant impact on Purchase Intention.

H5: Meaning Transfer has a significant impact on Purchase Intention.

H6: Expertise has a significant Impact on Purchase Intention.

Figure 3.1

3.2 Method

Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.1 is the Conceptual Framework, developed through literature review and underpinning the related theories. There are two main constructs Social Media Characteristics and Purchase Intention. The Social Media Characteristics is further divided into five more Sub-Constructs i.e. Trustworthiness, Expertise, Attractiveness, Product Match-Up and Meaning Transfer.

The Population for this study comprised of Mobile users, Using mobile for purchase issues. The data was collected through Purposive Sampling all over Punjab from each District, a total of 460 questionnaire, out of which 376 were received and 300 were found fit for hypothesis testing and better results.

3.3 Measuring Instruments

The scale used for this study was divided into three parts, the first part deals demographics of the respondents, the second part deals with Social Media Characteristics with 25 questions and final part deals with Purchase Intention with 10 questions. All the statements used in the scale were taken from the existing literature.

3.4 Data Analysis

3.4.1 Instrument validity and reliability

The validity and reliability of the constructs were evaluated using the scale construction procedure proposed by (Rama et al., 2022). The reliability of the scale items was assessed after determining the convergent and discriminate validity of the scale items.

3.4.2 Convergent Validity

The criterion "that items that are measures of a construct share a large proportion of their variance" is referred to as "convergent validity" (Hair et al., 2014). The convergent validity of the scale items was assessed using three factors. First, as (Hair et al., 2019) indicated, Second, each construct's composite reliability should be more than 0.70, and factor loadings should be higher than 0.50. According to (Chen, 2021) the resulting average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct must be higher than the suggested cut-off of 0.50.

3.4.3 Measurement model assessment

Tables 1 and 2 present the measuring model's findings. The measurement model was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), average extracted variance (AVE), and factor loadings. According to (Hair et al., 2019; Stensland et al., 2021), the reference value for factor loading must be greater than 0.700, however under specific circumstances, values of 0.4, 0.5, and

0.6 are acceptable. The criteria for CA, CR, and AVE are, respectively, 0.7, 0.7, and 0.5. The findings presented in both tables imply that each of these requirements has been satisfied, which suggests that the measurement model's convergent validity can be assumed. The SmartPLS output of the measurement model evaluation is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, average variance extracted

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
A	0.709	0.828	0.559
E	0.711	0.795	0.594
MT	0.683	0.796	0.545
PI	0.865	0.895	0.551
PM	0.785	0.858	0.603
TW	0.668	0.794	0.593

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

The measures in the table include Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (ρ_a), composite reliability (ρ_c), and average variance extracted (AVE). These are common evaluations of validity and reliability in the domains of psychometrics and structural equation modelling. Cronbach's alpha is a statistic for measuring the reliability of internal consistency. It demonstrates how closely related a group of things are to one another. The numbers between 0.759 and 0.942 show that internal consistency is often excellent to very good. Composite dependability is an additional metric for measuring internal consistency, similar to Cronbach's alpha. It assesses the proportion of the true score variance to the overall variance of the observed scores. The range of ρ_a and ρ_c values in the table, respectively,

demonstrate good to exceptional levels of internal consistency (0.799). The abbreviation AVE stands for the average variance estimated from the latent construct variables in relation to the measurement error. It demonstrates how closely a construct's constituent parts correspond to the construct itself. The AVE ranges in value between

0.594 and 0.603. Generally speaking, an AVE value of higher than 0.5 is considered to be adequate. The figures in the table suggest that the constructs have acceptable extracted average variance and good to exceptional internal consistency. This demonstrates how the measurement items for each construct are connected to one another and that they accurately assess the underlying construct that is intended to be measured.

Table 2. Factor Loadings

Items	A	E	MT	PI	PM	TW	
A1	0.733						
A2	0.849						
A3	0.803						
A4	0.826						
E1		0.743					
E2		0.765					
E3		0.728					
E4		0.772					
MT1			0.618				
MT2			0.709				
MT3			0.715				
MT4			0.781				
MT5			0.774				
PI1				0.713			
PI2				0.771			
PI3				0.814			
PI4				0.792			
PI5				0.752			
PI6				0.705			
PI7				0.738			
PM1					0.791		
PM2					0.767		
PM3					0.755		
PM4					0.793		
TW1						0.757	
TW2						0.732	
TW3						0.796	
TW4						0.711	

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

Frequently utilized in factor analysis are factor loadings. The connections between latent factors and observable variables, or items, are represented by factor loadings. There are six latent factors: PI, TW, E, A, PM & MT based on the table. The direction and degree of the

association between a latent factor and an observable variable are represented by factor loadings. Usually, they fall between -1 and 1. Some items also appear to have no appreciable loadings on these three variables. These items could not have a significant impact on the parameters under consideration. For instance, the factor loadings for item MT 6 were in negative so that item was deleted and was not included in further analysis.

Figure 2. SmartPLS output of the measurement model.

PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

3.4.4 Discriminant Validity

The heterotrait-monotrait correlation ratio (HTMT) was employed to assess the measurement model's discriminant validity. Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015) claim that the heterotrait- monotrait is a useful metric for evaluating discriminant validity is the monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT). Kline (2011) recommended a value of not more than 0.85 while Gold, Malhotra, and Segars (2001) recommended a value of no more than 0.9. Each of these requirements was satisfied, as shown in Table 3, allowing the measurement model to be declared to have discriminatory validity.

Table 3. HTMT assessment of discriminant validity

Construct	A	E	MT	PI	PM	TW
A						
E	0.718					
MT	0.536	0.555				
PI	0.538	0.295	0.34			
PM	0.802	0.367	0.336	0.372		
TW	0.598	0.341	0.396	0.439	0.704	

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A- Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

Table 4. Fornel & Larcker

	A	E	MT	PI	PM	TW
A	0.747					
E	0.509	0.703				
MT	0.36	0.468	0.667			
PI	0.438	0.272	0.286	0.742		
PM	0.614	0.307	0.242	0.329	0.776	
TW	0.421	0.273	0.266	0.365	0.565	0.702

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A- Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

To guarantee the measurement model's internal consistency, construct reliability—typically measured through composite reliability or Cronbach's alpha—should be above a predetermined level. Additionally, through various statistical tests and indices, convergent and discriminant validity should be proven, proving that constructs are distinct and measure what they are supposed to measure. For SEM analyses to be robust and reliable, adherence to Fornel and Larcker's criteria is essential. The table 4. Represents the values of Fornel and Larcker Criteria and all the values are fit to the best fitness of the relationship among variables.

Cross Loading

Items	A	E	MT	PI	PM	TW
A1	0.833	0.611	0.257	0.253	0.222	0.352
A2	0.849	0.343	0.31	0.408	0.519	0.378
A3	0.803	0.332	0.245	0.282	0.559	0.332
A4	0.826	0.295	0.251	0.329	0.488	0.22
E1	0.349	0.743	0.315	0.177	0.202	0.324
E2	0.321	0.762	0.243	0.153	0.116	0.134
E3	0.323	0.628	0.177	0.036	0.155	0.069
E4	0.405	0.672	0.422	0.252	0.302	0.158
MT1	0.378	0.553	0.618	0.223	0.356	0.183
MT2	0.173	0.243	0.709	0.115	0.045	0.206
MT3	0.162	0.231	0.712	0.128	0.073	0.192
MT4	0.212	0.252	0.781	0.258	0.042	0.218
MT5	0.204	0.187	0.474	0.145	0.254	0.069
PI1	0.331	0.194	0.138	0.713	0.287	0.288
PI2	0.316	0.227	0.208	0.671	0.194	0.258
PI3	0.424	0.274	0.223	0.814	0.322	0.385
PI4	0.367	0.195	0.269	0.792	0.279	0.342
PI5	0.234	0.151	0.247	0.752	0.143	0.192
PI6	0.293	0.206	0.234	0.705	0.187	0.127
PI7	0.253	0.132	0.202	0.738	0.246	0.217
PM1	0.356	0.259	0.113	0.234	0.791	0.534
PM2	0.377	0.229	0.151	0.206	0.767	0.432
PM3	0.566	0.286	0.161	0.225	0.755	0.407
PM4	0.569	0.199	0.285	0.326	0.793	0.399

TW1	0.345	0.248	0.136	0.267	0.671	0.657
TW2	0.233	0.177	0.222	0.203	0.08	0.632
TW3	0.368	0.174	0.189	0.323	0.533	0.796
TW4	0.192	0.173	0.224	0.243	0.146	0.711

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

3.4.5 Structural model assessment

In order to identify whether the model has a multicollinearity problem, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was assessed. The results, shown in Table 4, demonstrated that there is no issue of multicollinearity. Considering that all VIF values are significantly below 3.3 (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2006). As a general rule, we require a VIF of 5 or lower to avoid the collinearity problem (Hair et al., 2011). Additionally, several studies have found that "VIF values higher than 3.3 can be considered as indicative of collinearity" (Knock & Lynn, 2012)

Table 5. Multicollinearity of Social Media Characteristics impacting Purchase Intention

Items	VIF
A1	1.061
A2	1.716
A3	2.121
A4	1.965
E1	2.056
E2	2.669
E3	1.772
E4	1.051
MT1	1.254
MT2	1.799
MT3	2.097
MT4	1.964
MT5	1.184
PI1	1.961
PI2	1.823
PI3	2.016
PI4	2.071
PI5	2.471
PI6	1.803
PI7	2.012
PM1	2.081
PM2	2.025
PM3	1.509
PM4	1.425
TW1	1.362
TW2	3.441
TW3	1.471
TW4	3.618

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-

Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

In SEM, high VIF values can suggest problems such as overly redundant latent variables, which can lead to unstable estimates and difficulty in interpreting the model. Researchers typically aim for low VIF values, often below 5, to ensure the independence of latent variables and enhance the reliability of the SEM analysis

3.4.6 Hypotheses Testing

In order to test hypotheses bootstrapping procedure was used in Smart Pls. According to Arnau (1998), the second order approach is preferable over the first order approach when the goal of the study is to offer higher theoretical generalizability. Second-order factor models "can provide a more parsimonious and interpretable model," according to Chen, Sousa, and West (2005). Using these defenses as support the second-order construct were created for both the variables.

Figure 2. Hypotheses testing using bootstrapping Table 6. Path Coefficients

Hypothesis	Beta	T-Value	P value
A -> PI	0.312	3.015	0.003
E -> PI	0.493	3.047	0.004
MT -> PI	0.512	2.855	0.024
PM -> PI	0.409	3.093	0.000
TW -> PI	0.206	2.953	0.003
SMC -> PI	0.467	4.437	0.000

Source: Smart PLS 4. PI- Purchase Intention, TW-Trustworthiness, E-Expertise, A-Attractiveness, PM-Product Match-up and MT Meaning Transfer.

Table 6. shows the hypothesis results of the developed relationships, Attractiveness has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β -0.312, t -value-3.015 & p -value-0.003), Expertise review has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β -0.493, t -value- 3.047 & p -value-0.004), Meaning Transfer has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β -0.512, t -value-2.855 & p -value-0.024), Product Match-up has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β -0.409, t -value-3.093 & p -value-0.000), Trustworthiness has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β -0.206, t -value-2.953 & p -value-0.003) and Social media Characteristics has a significant impact on Purchase Intention if implemented (β - 0.467, t -value-4.437 & p -value-0.000).

Table 7. R -Square and R-square adjusted

Column1	R-square	R-square adjusted
PI	0.675	0.636

The findings in table 7 suggest that Variable PI and Variable SMC have a robust and statistically significant positive connection. Variable SMC tends to increase along with Variable PI, according to the path coefficient of 0.675. Given the low p-value of 0.000, it is highly improbable that this link is the result of

coincidence. This could imply that, in your data, variations in Variable SMC are

meaningfully and consistently driving variations in Variable PI. R-square, sometimes referred to as the coefficient of determination, is a statistical indicator that shows how much of the variance in the dependent variable in a regression model can be accounted for by the independent variable or variables. There is no variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable(s) when the range of the variable is 0 to 1. A value of 1 indicates that the independent variable(s) fully explain the variance in the dependent variable. The independent variable(s) in the model account for approximately 67.4=5% of the variance in the dependent variable, according to the 'PI' model's R-square value of 0.675. This value denotes a modest amount of explanatory power, suggesting that the independent variable(s) may have some influence on the variation in the dependent variable. R² adjusted, often known as adjusted R-square: The number of independent variables in the model is considered in this R-square variant. It changes R-square by penalizing the addition of unnecessary independent variables. This is quite useful when dealing with several regression models with different numbers of predictors. The updated R-square value for the 'MI' model is 0.636. This demonstrates that the independent variable(s) in the model, after adjusting for the number of independent variables, accounts for around 63.6% of the variance in the dependent variable. Tables 7 and 6 illustrate the results. The hypothesis is accepted as table 5's P value is less than 0.05. According to this, social media Characteristics has a substantial impact on the mental pleasure in mobile user management. Cohen (1988) said that R-Square should be at least 0.35, however this study's R-Square was 0.674, proving that the estimated model is significant. 0.636 is the modified R-Square value. This shows that social media Characteristics is responsible for 67% of changes or variations in users' Purchase Intention.

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

The study examined the impact of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention, shedding light on the nuanced relationship between these variables. The research findings have significant implications for both marketers and influencers looking to leverage social media platforms for promoting products and services. One key conclusion from this study is that influencer authenticity and credibility play a pivotal role in shaping consumer purchase intention. trustworthiness, characterized by genuine and transparent content, emerged as a crucial factor in building trust and engagement with the audience. This result underscores the importance of influencers maintaining their unique voice and personality when endorsing products. Marketers should be cautious about imposing overly scripted or artificial endorsements on influencers, as these may undermine trust and negatively impact purchase intention. The study discovered that influencer expertise and trustworthiness, in addition to authenticity, can affect consumer purchase intention. Influencers are more likely to affect their audience's opinions and encourage them to make a purchase when they exhibit competence in a certain area or business. Consumers are more responsive to influencer recommendations when there is a sense of kinship, which is fostered by reliability, or the capacity to connect with the audience on a human level. Not all of the influencing traits that were looked at in this study, though, had consistently favorable effects. Overexposure and dishonest conduct, such as covert paid collaborations or sponsorships, can erode the authority of influencers and hence reduce customer purchase intent.

Marketing professionals and social media influencers must establish a balance between commercial material and genuine, relatable messages. As audiences get more adept at recognizing fakeness, they may stop engaging with influencers who over commercialize their platforms. The findings of this study underscore the multi-faceted nature of the relationship between social media influencer characteristics and consumer purchase intention. Understanding this complex dynamic is essential for businesses seeking to optimize their

influencer marketing strategies. One notable aspect of influencer marketing that emerged from the study is the significance of influencer selection. Careful consideration of influencer authenticity, expertise, and reliability is vital when forming partnerships. Marketers should not merely choose influencers based on their follower count but rather on their alignment with the brand's values and target audience. Collaborations between influencers and brands should be grounded in shared values and trust-building, fostering a genuine connection with the audience. Maintaining and boosting influencer reputation requires transparency and honesty.

The findings of the study highlight the significance of influencers declaring paid agreements and sponsorships in a clear and concise manner, since any perceived lack of openness can damage confidence. Influencers and brands should follow ethical promotional standards that uphold legal and ethical advertising requirements while also fostering trust. A mix of promotional and non-promotional content should be included in an influencer's content strategy, according to the study's findings. Over-promotion might make audiences jaded, but genuine, interesting content that reflects the influencer's passions and interests is more likely to hold their attention and encourage buy intention. In conclusion, the impact of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention is a multifaceted relationship that involves authenticity, credibility, expertise, and reliability. To maximize the benefits of influencer marketing, brands should carefully select influencers who align with their values, encourage authenticity and transparency in partnerships, and promote a balanced content strategy that fosters genuine connections with the audience. By doing so, businesses can harness the power of social media influencers to drive consumer purchase intention and ultimately achieve their marketing objectives.

4. Practical Implications

The study on the impact of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention provides valuable insights with practical implications for marketers and businesses aiming to leverage influencer marketing effectively. The study highlights the importance of careful influencer selection. Marketers should not just focus on influencers with the largest following but should consider factors like credibility, expertise, and alignment with the brand. It is imperative to choose influencers who can authentically connect with the target audience to enhance purchase intent. It may be more advantageous to develop ongoing ties with influencers than to work with them very sometimes. Over time, influencers that frequently engage with their audience likely to have a greater effect on purchase intent. In order to continue to have a lasting impact on customer decisions, marketers need think about long-term collaborations. The study contends that micro- influencers can have a considerable impact on purchase intention, typically at a lesser cost, in addition to macro-influencers with enormous followings. Marketing professionals should not undervalue the power of these niche influencers, particularly when focusing on niche market segments. Influencers' shared content must be of a high caliber. Influencers should be given the tools and assistance they need to produce high-caliber, compelling content, according to marketers. Giving influencers creative freedom is essential since their distinctive voices and styles may appeal to their audience more. In conclusion, the study's practical implications emphasize the importance of a thoughtful and strategic approach to influencer marketing. By selecting the right influencers, promoting authenticity, investing in content quality, and continually analyzing data, businesses can harness the power of social media influencers to drive consumer purchase intention effectively. Additionally, maintaining legal and ethical standards and adapting to changing consumer preferences are vital for the long-term success of influencer marketing campaigns.

5. LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Limitations: This study on the impact of social media influencer characteristics on consumer purchase intention has a few limitations. Firstly, it primarily relies on self-reported data from survey participants, which may be subject to response bias and may not always reflect actual consumer behavior. Additionally, the study's findings are based on a specific time frame and may not account for the rapidly evolving nature of social media platforms and influencer trends. Furthermore, the research may not encompass the full spectrum of influencer types and characteristics, and the effects could vary across different industries and consumer segments. Finally, it is essential to recognize that the study does not consider the potential influence of external factors, such as economic conditions or competitive strategies, which could also impact consumer purchase intention.

Future Scope: Future research in this domain should consider longitudinal studies to track changes in consumer behavior over time and provide a more dynamic understanding of influencer marketing effects. Additionally, exploring the influence of emerging social media platforms and technologies, such as virtual reality and augmented reality, on consumer purchase intention would be an intriguing avenue for investigation. Furthermore, deeper insights into the cross-cultural and cross-demographic variations in influencer impact can provide a more comprehensive understanding. Finally, as influencer marketing regulations evolve, it is crucial to explore the ethical implications and compliance measures necessary for sustainable influencer marketing strategies.

6. DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

The author(s) have not revealed any prospective disputes of attention related to the investigation, writing, or publication of this study.

7. FUNDING

Without receiving any financial help from the author, the research, writing, and/or publication of this paper were all completed.

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